

EUCALL

The European Cluster of Advanced Laser Light Sources

Grant Agreement number: 654220

Work package 7 – Work package PUCCA

Deliverable D7.7

CDR to build a wavefront sensor for [8-25] keV

Lead Beneficiary: ESRF

Authors:

PART I: Elena-Ruxandra Cojocaru¹, Sebastien Berujon¹, Eric Ziegler¹
¹ESRF (WP7: PUCCA)

Contributing authors: Jonas Schenke², Michael Bussmann²
²HZDR (WP5: UFDAC)

PART II: Michele Manfredda³, Lorenzo Raimondi³, Marco Zangrando³
³FERMI (WP7: PUCCA)

Part III: M. Ruiz-Lopez⁴, B. Keitel⁴, M. Kuhlmann⁴, S. Dzarzhytski⁴, E. Plönjes⁴, T. Wodzinski⁵, J. Chalupský⁶,
T. Burian⁶, V. Vozda⁶, L. Vyšín⁶, V. Hájková⁶, L. Juha⁶, M. Zangrando³, L. Raimondi³, L. Samoylova⁷
⁴DESY, ⁵IPFN Lisbon, ⁶Institute of Physics, AS CR Prague, ⁷European XFEL

Due date: 30 September 2018

Date of delivery: 25 September 2018

Project webpage: www.eucall.eu

<i>Deliverable Type</i>	
R = Report DEM = Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs DEC = Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc. OTHER = Software, technical diagram, etc.	R
<i>Dissemination Level</i>	
PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web CO = Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement CI = Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	PU

LUND UNIVERSITY

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 654220

Contents

I. Speckle-based Wavefront Sensor for the Hard X-ray Regime	4
1. Introduction	5
1.1. X-ray Facilities and Applications	5
1.2. X-ray Wavefront Sensing	6
2. X-ray Speckle Tracking Principle and Software Package	7
2.1. X-ray Speckle Tracking Principle	7
2.2. Detector Calibration and Computation of the Detector Distortion	9
2.3. Computing the Wavefront	13
2.4. Benchmarking Results	15
2.5. Multi-core Parallelization of the Wavefront Reconstruction Algorithm	17
3. Description of the Instrument	19
3.1. Short Overview of the Instrument	19
3.2. Detectors	21
3.2.1. Cameras and triggering	21
3.2.2. Scintillators	22
3.2.3. Semi-transparent mirrors	24
3.3. Speckle membrane optimization	26
3.3.1. Diamond membrane	29
3.4. Detector Distortion	30
4. Experiments and Results	31
4.1. Commissioning at the ESRF Beamline BM05	31
4.2. Experiments at the FXE instrument of the European XFEL	34
4.3. Experiment at the XPP instrument of the LCLS	39
5. Conclusions and Outlook	42
5.1. Synergy aspects	43
6. Acknowledgements	44

II. Activity report on Wavefront sensing at FERMI	47
III. Report on Focal spot characterization using wavefront sensors at FLASH2 and WavePropagator Code	51

Part I.

Speckle-based Wavefront Sensor for the Hard X-ray Regime

Authors: Elena-Ruxandra Cojocaru, Sebastien Berujon and Eric Ziegler

Contributing authors: Jonas Schenke and Michael Bussmann

1. Introduction

1.1. X-ray Facilities and Applications

X-rays define a specific region of the electromagnetic spectrum characterized by a very short wavelength ranging from 0.01 nm to 10 nm. This makes them suitable for probing structures much smaller than those usually accessible with visible light. X-ray photons carry a sufficient amount of energy to ionize atoms and disrupt molecular bonds. Due to these properties, they contribute to a vast range of applications, in fields such as material science, chemistry, medicine and life sciences, environmental and earth sciences and even in cultural heritage studies.

The first ever and still the most commonly used X-ray source is the X-ray tube, initially developed at the end of the 19th century. The next major source for X-rays is synchrotron radiation, demonstrated experimentally in the 1940s using a tabletop system followed by the appearance in the 1970s of machines dedicated to applied science. Although synchrotrons represent a far larger and more expensive alternative to regular laboratory X-ray sources, the possibility of hosting up to 50-60 experiments simultaneously reduces the cost price. Synchrotron radiation offers the advantage of a highly collimated and much brighter beam with tunable energy. Currently, diffraction-limited storage rings have opened (MAX IV) or are planned (ESRF, Sirius, PETRA IV, Diamond, APS, Soleil, SPring8) around the world. The substantial reduction of emittance with respect to previous synchrotron accelerator lattices results in an increase of the brightness and horizontal transverse coherence by one order of magnitude or more and in a decrease of the pulse duration [1].

On the other hand, other technologies are employed to develop new types of X-ray sources, such as laser-powered sources or X-ray free electron lasers (large scale facilities such as SACLA, LCLS, European XFEL). These sources aim at producing ultrashort pulses in order to enable the probing of ultrafast processes such as the formation or breakup of chemical bonds. In total, 60 synchrotrons and free electron lasers facilities are currently in operation or under construction in the world.

1.2. X-ray Wavefront Sensing

One challenge in the case of imaging applications, whatever the technology employed for generating X-rays, is to find a suitable tool for wavefront metrology. Online metrology is crucial to characterize the influence of optical components present along the beam and optimize its properties. Some of the current most popular choices for wavefront sensing are the Hartmann and grating-based sensors, e.g. [2–5]. Although effective, these instruments suffer from a number of drawbacks such as a limited spatial resolution dependent on the grid used or the pitch of the grating and the need for a delicate calibration to account for wavefront modulator imperfections. An alternative technology suitable for the hard X-ray regime (energy $\gtrsim 10$ keV, or wavelength < 0.12 nm) is a speckle-based wavefront sensing approach. A device based on this principle can overcome some of the disadvantages of the competing technologies [6].

In the frame of the EUCALL WP, Pulse Characterisation and Control (PUCCA) project, the ESRF is designing a wavefront sensor prototype for the hard X-ray energy regime based on the principle of X-ray speckle tracking. Alongside this instrument, we also developed a dedicated and versatile software package for wavefront retrieval and reconstruction from speckle experimental data.

The present report is structured as follows: Chapter 2 presents the working principle behind our instrument, gives details regarding the experimental workflow and detector calibration, and describes our software implementation for wavefront computation, including a study on software optimization possibilities as a contribution of our colleagues from EUCALL WP5, Ultrafast Data Acquisition (UFDAC); Ch. 3 describes the instrument and its main components; Ch. 4 gives an overview of the experimental campaigns through which the instrument was tested at three different large-scale X-ray facilities; finally, Ch. 5 presents our main conclusions and Ch. 6 acknowledges the effort of all those involved in this project.

2. X-ray Speckle Tracking Principle and Software Package

2.1. X-ray Speckle Tracking Principle

Figure 2.1: XST principle [7]

The X-ray Speckle Tracking (XST) principle relies on using speckle grains as markers of the trajectory of the X-rays. In brief, by considering two speckle images, a cross-correlation algorithm can identify small subsets of pixels from the first image in the second, from which the wavefront gradient is eventually recovered. Then, through bidimensional integration, the wavefront is reconstructed.

Thus, a key component of the XST method is the cross-correlation algorithm. To fulfil this function, we use the *TemplateMatching* algorithm implemented in C++, interfaced for Python through the OpenCV2 library [8]. This algorithm looks for a small template subset T , of size $a \cdot b$, in a larger search area A , of size $m \cdot n$, and returns a correlation matrix, of size $(m - a + 1) \cdot (n - b + 1)$. This matrix contains numerical values from -1 to 1, where values close to 1 represent a strong correlation and values close to -1 represent a strong anti-correlation. The computation of the cross-correlation matrix calls for a cross-correlation criterion. In XST, we use a normalized correlation coefficient-based criterion (`method = cv2.TM_CCORF_NORMED` in the *TemplateMatching* code [9]):

$$R(x, y) = \frac{\sum_{x', y'} (T'(x', y') \cdot A'(x + x', y + y'))}{\sqrt{\sum_{x', y'} (T'(x', y'))^2 \cdot \sum_{x', y'} (A'(x + x', y + y'))^2}} \quad (2.1)$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} T'(x', y') &= T(x', y') - \frac{1}{w \cdot h} \sum_{x'', y''} T(x'', y'') \\ A'(x', y') &= A(x + x', x + y') - \frac{1}{w \cdot h} \sum_{x'', y''} A(x + x'', x + y'') \end{aligned} \quad (2.2)$$

The correlation matrix returned by the template matching algorithm is then used to compute the relative displacement of the central position of the template subset relative to the central position of the search area. To obtain the full displacement map, all template subsets centered onto pixels of a grid of Image 1 must be searched for in corresponding search areas in Image 2 (Fig. 2.2 illustrates the flow diagram of the corresponding subroutine in our code, *cross_spot*). This process involves a *first* and a *second pass*. In the *first pass*, a coarse grid is applied to the image, centering a template subset in each pixel of this grid in Image 1 with a corresponding larger search area in Image 2. Assuming a rigid translation between the two images, it is necessary to correct for this when defining the position of the search area. This is the role of the parameter called *mode*. Next, all template subsets and corresponding search areas are run through the cross-correlation algorithm. An initial pixel-accurate displacement map is computed and is interpolated to obtain a value for all image pixels and not only those of the coarse grid. Later, the *second pass* is run, defined on a finer grid. This second pass consists of a loop where parameters, such as the template subset size, are optimized. In practice, the template subset size is gradually increased from one iteration to the other to gain in robustness: the cross-correlation is run several times for certain points with weak correlation peak values, until the errors in each control point are satisfactorily minimized. Finally, the obtained displacement maps are again interpolated for all the pixels in the image to recover the original sampling resolution. This section of the code is one of the most time consuming parts of the program. For this reason it was the object of the optimization efforts presented in Sec. 2.5.

Figure 2.2: *cross_spot* subroutine workflow diagram

2.2. Detector Calibration and Computation of the Detector Distortion

A wavefront sensing experiment employing our instrument can be divided in two main parts as sketched in Fig. 2.3: an initial calibration phase and afterwards a measurement cycle. The calibration requires first the collection of dark images, i.e. without X-ray beam, with the same duration as for the future measurements that will be averaged. The resulting image, I_{dark} , is used to account and partially correct for the electronic noise inherent to the detector camera. Afterwards, a set of flat images without the membrane is recorded at different transverse positions of the detector with respect to the beam. This time, the averaged flat image, I_{flat} , is used to remove the defects present in the visible light scintillator. When two detectors are used, these steps have to be performed for each detector. Later on, every measured speckle image is corrected as follows:

$$I_{speckle} = \frac{I_{raw} - I_{dark}}{I_{flat} - I_{dark}} \quad (2.3)$$

Figure 2.3: Experiment and data workflows

An important step for the detector calibration is the characterization of its distortion, in order to correct for the aberrations arising from the optical components of the imaging detector. This well-defined detector distortion calibration protocol represents one of the important advantages offered by a speckle-based wavefront sensor over its competitors that tend to elude the issue [6]. In practice, this calibration process requires images collected by moving each detector in an equally-spaced two-dimensional mesh grid in the transversal plane with respect to the beam. Mathematically, the distortion-free image, (x_r, y_r) , can be defined by a function, $f = (f_x, f_y)$, of its distorted equivalent, (x_d, y_d) :

$$x_r = x_d + f_x(x_d, y_d)$$

$$y_r = y_d + f_y(x_d, y_d)$$

When subjecting the detector to a translation (corresponding to the step of the grid in each direction), for example in the x direction, $\mathbf{h}_x = h \cdot \mathbf{e}_x$, this translates into a displacement vector, \mathbf{v}_{xy} :

$$\mathbf{v}_{xy} \cdot \mathbf{e}_x = \frac{1}{s_{pix}} [h + f_x(x_d + h, y_d) - f_x(x_d, y_d)]$$

$$\mathbf{v}_{xy} \cdot \mathbf{e}_y = \frac{1}{s_{pix}} [f_y(x_d + h, y_d) - f_y(x_d, y_d)]$$

where s_{pix} is the detector pixel size. In the case of a translation in the y direction, $\mathbf{h}_y = h \cdot \mathbf{e}_y$, the displacement vector, \mathbf{v}'_{xy} , will be:

$$\mathbf{v}'_{xy} \cdot \mathbf{e}_x = \frac{1}{s_{pix}} [f_x(x_d, y_d + h) - f_x(x_d, y_d)]$$

$$\mathbf{v}'_{xy} \cdot \mathbf{e}_y = \frac{1}{s_{pix}} [h + f_y(x_d, y_d + h) - f_y(x_d, y_d)]$$

By assuming $s_{pix} = \frac{h}{\langle |\mathbf{v}_{xy}| \rangle_{(x,y)}}$, the approximate directional derivatives of (f_x, f_y) , corresponding to the four gradient maps, is obtained by forward difference:

$$\nabla_x f_x(x, y) = \frac{\partial f_x}{\partial x} \Big|_{(x,y)} = \frac{\mathbf{v}_{xy} \cdot \mathbf{e}_x - \langle |\mathbf{v}_{xy}| \rangle}{\langle |\mathbf{v}_{xy}| \rangle}$$

$$\nabla_x f_y(x, y) = \frac{\partial f_y}{\partial x} \Big|_{(x,y)} = \frac{\mathbf{v}_{xy} \cdot \mathbf{e}_y}{\langle |\mathbf{v}_{xy}| \rangle}$$

$$\nabla_y f_x(x, y) = \frac{\partial f_x}{\partial y} \Big|_{(x,y)} = \frac{\mathbf{v}'_{xy} \cdot \mathbf{e}_x}{\langle |\mathbf{v}'_{xy}| \rangle}$$

$$\nabla_y f_y(x, y) = \frac{\partial f_y}{\partial y} \Big|_{(x,y)} = \frac{\mathbf{v}'_{xy} \cdot \mathbf{e}_y - \langle |\mathbf{v}'_{xy}| \rangle}{\langle |\mathbf{v}'_{xy}| \rangle}$$

Finally, the distortion functions are computed through the numerical integration of the gradient map pairs $(\nabla_x f_x, \nabla_y f_x)$ and $(\nabla_y f_x, \nabla_y f_y)$ to find the intermediate function (f'_x, f'_y) and then setting the integration constants to zero:

$$J_1 = \int \int \left(\frac{\partial f'_x}{\partial x} - \nabla_x f_x \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial f'_x}{\partial y} - \nabla_y f_x \right)^2 dx dy$$

$$J_2 = \int \int \left(\frac{\partial f'_y}{\partial x} - \nabla_x f_y \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial f'_y}{\partial y} - \nabla_y f_y \right)^2 dx dy$$

By computing these two distortion maps, one can undistort the speckle images as if they were recorded by perfect detector grids. That calibration protocol also allows for a precise calculation of the detector effective pixel size. Within the software package, the computing of the detector distortion maps is the role of one of the two core modules, named *detectorDistortion.py*, illustrated as a flow-diagram in Fig. 2.4. This module operates as a double loop through the images collected when moving the detector in the mesh grid to compare pairs of images in the horizontal and vertical direction using the *cross_spot* subroutine. Next, the four resulting displacement maps are integrated two by two to generate distortion maps for the horizontal and vertical directions.

Figure 2.4: Detector Distortion workflow diagram

2.3. Computing the Wavefront

The other main core module of the code, *waveFront.py*, is processing each measured pair of images in order to retrieve and reconstruct the wavefront, either in differential or absolute modes. This module is illustrated in Fig. 2.5. The main steps consist of:

- (i) Image corrections, namely dark and flat fields corrections, to undistort the images.
- (ii) Computing the displacement maps between the pair of images, again using the *cross_spot* subroutine.
- (iii) Numerical integration of the resulting displacement maps to finally obtain the reconstructed wavefront.

For numerical integration purposes, our software package offers two options: an implementation of the Frankot-Challappa algorithm [10] using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) or the grad2surf algorithm [11, 12], translated into the Python language [13].

Overall, our wavefront recovery and reconstruction software package was developed such as to present several key features:

- open-sourced language, the reason for choosing the Python language;
- flexibility, to facilitate the use of different data formats;
- versatility, for the code to be usable for different metrology modes and expandable for different wavefront recovery methods;
- completeness, to address both the calibration and reconstruction steps;
- potential for optimization in order to achieve near real-time processing (see Sec. 2.5 for discussion)

Figure 2.5: Wavefront Reconstruction workflow diagram

2.4. Benchmarking Results

CONTRIBUTING AUTHORS: JONAS SCHENKE AND MICHAEL BUSSMANN

All benchmarks were run on the Haswell partition of the Taurus supercomputer at the Technische Universität Dresden. Technical details on how these benchmarking computations were performed can be found in [14].

Each configuration used consisted of a dataset and core count. The times presented here for each configuration represent an average over five runs that started after four initial warm-up runs. In each case, the pure execution times of the scripts and individual functions were recorded. From these, input/output (I/O) times were excluded. The number of cores was varied from one to twenty-four and each benchmark ran exclusively on one node. To evaluate the performance of the present implementation, several types of data sets were used, however here we will only show the results obtained using the data sets from [15] measured in differential mode.

To identify bottlenecks and particularly time-consuming functions, the program execution times and total number of function calls were logged. An overview of the complete program with its subroutines and their share of the total computation time is shown in Fig. 2.6a. This clearly shows that most of the computational time is needed for speckle tracking. A more detailed temporal distribution of the time consumed by each step involved in the speckle tracking process is shown in Fig. 2.6b. This shows that the second pass is the most demanding section of the code. The cumulative time of the top five most computational-intensive functions from all configurations (shown in Fig. 2.6c) adds up to more than 95% of the total time.

Figure 2.6: Percentage of runtime consumed by the main subroutines in the base Python code

The main reason why such long computation times (e.g. several minutes for one image pair when running on one core) are needed for the template matching process and subpixel interpolation is due to the elevated number of function calls. For example, a run involving 10 pairs of images (lenses - Set 1) resulted in over 22.5 million calls. In each of these calls, the template matching and subpixel interpolation are used only once. In addition, except for the template matching, the second run makes only minor use of already optimized libraries like numpy, that nevertheless increase the Python overhead.

Figure 2.7: Speedup of base Python implementation relative to the increase in the number of processing cores used

In the speckle tracking process, the calls within the second pass are parallelized by means of joblib. This uses the standard multiprocessing library, which creates a fork of the entire Python environment for each thread [16]. The high computation time needed for gradient integration is related to the size of the image used. Overall, the program has a poor CPU utilization of only 19.635% on average [17], which often means that some of the cores are not used at times or are only slightly used. This shows that much could be gained with further optimization.

2.5. Parallelization of the Wavefront Reconstruction Algorithm through Multi-core Processing

CONTRIBUTING AUTHORS: JONAS SCHENKE AND MICHAEL BUSSMANN

As part of his Bachelor thesis [14], J. Schenke studied several possibilities for parallelizing and then optimizing the code to ensure faster processing times. This included:

- parallelizing the processing of a batch of image pairs by means of MPI, by distributing each pair over a computational core.
- the use of parallel computing within the processing of an individual image pair by means of MPI.
- optimizing performance by eliminating bottlenecks within the Python version.

Fig. 2.8 shows a significant speed-up of the final MPI implementation when compared to the Python implementation. Tests performed using data sets containing CRL measurements in differential mode showed a maximum acceleration factor of 40 for Set 1.

During the course of this study, several more trivial optimization solutions have been implemented, ultimately showing that further potential in terms of optimization can be achieved. For example, node-internal communication could be done with intra-communicators or shared optimized memory to reduce the copying effort of the data. Although many optimization solutions have already been implemented in this work and a high speed-up has been achieved, more could be gained. restart numbering of figures after partIt would be possible to accelerate the gradient integration and also form data blocks based on the most frequently called functions, processing them in such a way that the overhead of the function calls decreases. Further processing of these data blocks by means of numpy, numexpr or numba could be attempted. The CUDA and OpenCL interfaces for numba could also be used here, implementing a General Purpose Computing on Graphics Processing Units (GPGPUs) outsource.

Another point to improve would be load balance. This would mean grouping the image pairs into packages and editing them one after the other so that a continuous operation could be achieved. Other optimizations of the algorithm are still conceivable, for example in the template matching part and the initial calibration.

Figure 2.8: Speedup of optimized implementation relative to the increase in the number of processing cores used

3. Description of the Instrument

3.1. Short Overview of the Instrument

Figure 3.1: Sketch of experimental setup for absolute wavefront metrology

The proposed prototype is a hard X-ray wavefront sensor based on the speckle tracking principle, and whose elements can be adapted to work with different types of X-ray sources and experimental configurations. To demonstrate this, we tested the instrument at three different X-ray facilities: the BM05 beamline of the ESRF, the Femtosecond X-Ray Experiments (FXE) instrument of the European XFEL and the X-ray Pump-Probe (XPP) instrument of the LCLS. More details on these experimental campaigns are given in Chapter 4. The considerations behind choosing certain specific components for our instrument are detailed in the present chapter.

We aim at providing a metrology instrument usable in two modes:

- (i) The differential mode permits the characterization of wavefront variations between consecutive measurements (e.g. for a high-repetition pulsed source) or variations generated by the introduction of new optical elements in the beam path. This mode allows for instance for the individual characterization of optical elements. It was used at the ESRF for the individual characterization of each X-ray refractive lens composing an optical system [15]. This configuration requires only one detector and one speckle membrane. When further X-ray measurements are desired downstream from the wavefront sensor, the optical arrangement composing the detector system has to be semi-transparent. Otherwise and more generally, the detector acts as a beamstop by absorbing fully the X-ray beam.
- (ii) The absolute wavefront measurement mode characterizes the global wavefront obtained from the contribution of all optical elements present along the beam. This mode is useful for overall beamline optimization measurements. However, it is also more demanding as it requires the use of two synchronized detectors plus a speckle membrane (see Fig. 3.1). In addition, the first detector optics must be semi-transparent and designed so that both detectors receive similar flux levels.

At a large-scale X-ray facility, the partial coherence of the beam is sufficient for applying the speckle tracking principle. The generation of near-field speckle as a random intensity pattern is then made possible by the interference between the directly transmitted beam and the waves scattered from a membrane that plays the role of a random phase object. The resulting speckle grains act as trajectory markers of the X-ray trajectories, eventually permitting the extraction of the two wavefront gradients, corresponding to the vertical and horizontal directions, from one single measurement. In a more general sense, the speckle membrane plays the same role of wavefront modulator as the grating does in other sensors. Nonetheless, the speckle membrane offers the advantage of being economical and much easier to supply for instance in case of beam damage or different feature size requirements (speckle size/grating pitch) for the experimental configurations, e.g. when using detectors with different pixel sizes.

Other speckle-based approaches and processing methods exist for wavefront retrieval. These alternative methods can provide higher resolution or/and sensitivity although at the cost of longer data collection times. Our code was designed for the X-ray speckle tracking method (XST), i.e. for comparing two speckle images obtained either in differential or absolute metrology modes. However, future work could permit the adaptation of the code to handle the X-ray speckle vector tracking method (XSVT) [18].

3.2. Detectors

Depending on the chosen metrology mode, our instrument requires one or two indirect-conversion X-ray detectors for micro-imaging. The overall scheme for such a detector is well known since the 1990s [19], typically consisting of a thin-film scintillator, a high-resolution visible light microscope objective and a camera. For the absolute metrology mode, where at least one semi-transparent detector is needed, one extra component is needed - a semi-transparent mirror tilted at 45 deg that allows part of the X-ray beam to pass while reflecting the visible light produced by the scintillator towards the camera mounted on the vertical axis, perpendicular to the beam (see Fig. 3.2). The following subsections discuss the main components of such a detector within the context of our instrument.

Figure 3.2: Semi-transparent detector: a) internal sketch; b) CAD model.

3.2.1. Cameras and triggering

For the absolute metrology mode, two cameras model PCO Edge 4.2 were used during the commissioning at BM05/ESRF and during the experiments at FXE/European XFEL. This sCMOS (CIS2020 sensor) camera model features a 2048 x 2048 pixels resolution, a high dynamic range 33 000:1 and a recording speed of up to 100 fps using a rolling shutter with an adjustable exposure time ranging from 500 μ s to 2 s. The sensor pixel size is 6.5 μ m \times 6.5 μ m. For the LCLS experiment, two Andor Zyla 5.5 cameras were used, having similar characteristics to the fore-mentioned PCO Edge cameras (sCMOS sensor, 2560 x 2160 pixels resolution, 25000:1

dynamic range, recording speed up to 40 fps with USB 3.0 connection, global and rolling shutters available).

For the absolute metrology mode, simultaneous hardware triggering of the cameras had to be ensured. For the ESRF and FXE/European XFEL experiments, Roberto Homs (ESRF) wrote a software patch to complement the official PCO Camware program to ensure that both cameras start taking pictures at the same time and in sync. To compensate for different internal processing times of the two cameras and insure that they start acquisition simultaneously, an OPIOM card was included in the triggering scheme.

To capture each individual pulse in differential metrology mode during the FXE/European XFEL experiments, we used a high-speed camera, UHS Hyper Vision HPV-X2 (Shimadzu Corporation, Japan). In order to achieve up to 5 Mfps recording speed, this camera employs a different read-out strategy, storing a limited number of images, up to a maximum of 128 frames, on a dedicated memory chip, that are then read out at a slower speed. The camera FTCMOS2 image sensor has 400×250 effective square pixels with a size of $32 \mu\text{m}$. The duration between frames can be tuned as multiples of 10 ns, offering variable frame rates from 60 fps to 2 Mfps. Image acquisition can be hardware triggered. However, the internal camera clock cannot be synchronized with an external one.

3.2.2. Scintillators

Two scintillator options have been selected. The first one, preferable for the lower hard X-ray energy regime, uses a YAG:Ce scintillator with a 70 ns decay and a 550 nm output wavelength. Such a scintillator is commercially available from Crytur, Czech Rep. Scintillators with two different thicknesses, $50 \mu\text{m}$ and $25 \mu\text{m}$, have been tested. The transmission performance at low energy, below 30 keV, was definitely better for the thinner scintillator.

For the higher energy regime, a LYSO:Ce scintillator was selected. This component, produced in-house at the ESRF, features a 41 ns decay time and a 420 nm output wavelength. In this ongoing project the lowest thickness for a free-standing scintillator is currently of $60 \mu\text{m}$. An alternative solution consisting of mounting the scintillator on an aluminum ring support would theoretically allow to reach a thickness of $40 \mu\text{m}$, although this option is still under evaluation. The LYSO:Ce material was selected for its short decay time and because it can offer a more balanced flux on both detectors at higher energies.

Figure 3.3: Scintillator transmission as a function of photon energy when mounting the sensor in a downstream configuration (only one semi-transparent detector). The black solid line marks the 50% lower threshold imposed on the scintillator transmission.

Depending on the specific needs of a particular experiment, the wavefront sensor can be mounted either upstream or downstream the experimental setup involved. We have tested the downstream option that requires only one semi-transparent detector. We found the YAG:Ce scintillator with 25 μm thickness to be best to use above an X-ray energy of 8.5 keV and the LYSO:Ce scintillator to use above an energy of 29 keV. These values are determined by imposing a 50% lower threshold on the transmission-energy curve shown in Fig. 3.3. Although the upper limit of the energy range for which our sensor has currently been commissioned is 25 keV, in practice the use of our wavefront sensor can be extended up to ~ 40 keV, according to tests performed at BM05/ESRF.

The other option is to place the wavefront upstream of a specific experiment. This option is overall more demanding as it would require two semi-transparent detectors. This could be effectively achieved only in a narrower energy range, as shown in Fig. 3.4. Considering the same 50% lower threshold on the overall transmission of the two scintillators that have to be taken into account for this configuration, the use of YAG:Ce scintillators with a 25 μm thickness is advised for energies between 11 keV and 17 keV or above 20.5 keV. The use of LYSO:Ce scintillators with an individual thickness of 60 μm is recommended for energies above 38 keV.

Figure 3.4: Scintillator transmission as a function of photon energy when mounting the sensor in an upstream configuration (two semi-transparent detectors). The black solid line marks the 50% lower threshold imposed on the scintillator transmission.

3.2.3. Semi-transparent mirrors

As previously mentioned, the absolute metrology mode is considerably more demanding as it requires two detectors. The first one consists of an indirect-conversion X-ray detector equipped with a semi-transparent optics in order to allow for a sufficiently high X-ray flux to reach the second detector. This condition proves more challenging in the lower range of the instrument's energy range, 8-10 keV. The transparency of the semi-transparent optics is influenced mainly by two components: the scintillator, for which we aim for at least 50% transmission as detailed in the previous section, and a support mirror that must be as transparent as possible. For the latter, we considered two options: a 4 mm thick vitreous carbon mirror or a mirror substrate made of either silica or stainless-steel substrate, pierced with a 1.5 mm diameter hole.

Figure 3.5: First detector overall transmission as a function of the photon energy, using a YAG:Ce scintillator, either 50 μm or 25 μm thick, and either a vitreous carbon mirror 4 mm thick or a pierced silica substrate mirror with a 1.5 mm diameter hole

Fig. 3.5 shows the overall transmission of the first detector, considering various mirrors and scintillator thicknesses. The best results are obtained with a 25 μm thick YAG:Ce scintillator and a pierced silica substrate mirror with a 1.5 mm diameter hole. When using the pierced mirror instead of the vitreous carbon the transmission in the 8-10 keV significantly improves from less than 5% to almost 20%. However, using the pierced mirror requires a delicate double alignment for the mirror plane to be exactly at 45 deg with respect to the plane of the camera sensor and for the hole to be aligned to maximize the transmitted flux. While the quality of this alignment impacts the detector’s overall transmission, this optimization is particularly difficult in the case of our current detector, as it is done manually. The production of such pierced mirrors proved also to be challenging for our suppliers, the silica substrate being difficult to pierce and the stainless-steel substrate being difficult to polish.

3.3. Speckle membrane optimization

During our experiments, we generally used PCO edge cameras with a $6.5\ \mu\text{m}$ pixel size and $5\times$ magnification microscope objectives to obtain an effective pixel size of approx. $1.3\ \mu\text{m}$. A rule of thumb for selecting a speckle membrane would be that the average speckle feature size should be at least 4 to 6 times larger than the effective pixel size for the speckle features to spread over a cluster of pixels.

Figure 3.6: Example of regions of 400×400 pixels from speckle images taken with different membranes

In order to choose the most suitable speckle membrane for our setup we considered several options: silica carbide membranes of different grit sizes (p80, p180, p360, p1200), cellulose nitrate with a $8\ \mu\text{m}$ pore size and cellulose acetate with a $1.2\ \mu\text{m}$ pore size. Examples of speckle images obtained with each of these membranes can be seen in Fig. 3.6. For each of these membranes we tried to compute the speckle feature size. There are different methods of computing this and several rely on the 2D autocorrelation function (ACF), that can be defined as [20]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 G(a, b) &= \sum_x^M \sum_y^N i(x, y) i(x - a, y - b) = \\
 &= F^{-1}[S(i)] = F^{-1}\{F[i(x, y)]F^*[i(x, y)]\},
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3.1}$$

where the initial image intensity I is normalized to zero mean and unit variance:

$$i = \frac{I - \bar{I}}{\sigma_I}
 \tag{3.2}$$

Figure 3.7: Example of ACF obtained for each membrane by averaging 400×400 regions over several images; the points corresponding to the FWHM and the first minimum are also displayed

Using the ACF, the speckle feature size can be determined as:

1. the full-width half maximum (FWHM) of the central peak [21];
2. the distance to the first minimum in the horizontal direction [22];
3. the half full-width of the central peak [23].

Of these, we chose to employ FWHM, as illustrated in Fig. 3.7, as it seems a more stable and objective method. Our results are presented alongside the average particle/pore size of the membrane in Table 3.1. Overall, we see a decrease in speckle size correlated with the decrease in the average particle/pore size of the membrane.

membrane	Particle/Pore size (μm)	Speckle size ($H \times V$) in μm
Silica carbide p80	201	5.8×4.0
Silica carbide p180	82	6.8×3.0
Silica carbide p360	40.5	6.2×3.8
Silica carbide p1200	15.3	5.6×2.9
Cellulose nitrate	8	4.4×2.1
Cellulose acetate	1.2	4.1×2.0

Table 3.1.: The speckle size obtained using the FWHM criterion for different membranes located at a distance of 555 mm from the detector (X-ray energy 16.5 keV)

The results for the silica carbide p80 membrane are particularly misleading, because although the speckle size seems quite low in this case, a quick inspection of Fig. 3.6a shows that in this case the feature size is not at all uniform, both large and small features being present. Here, the FWHM of the ACF only gives us the size of the smallest features. We can also observe that in the case of the silica carbide p180 and p360 the feature size is still not uniform enough, although at least in this case there is a correct correlation between the average particle size and the speckle size given by the FWHM of the ACF.

For the configuration using the PCO edge cameras and the $5\times$ microscope objective, the best performance was obtained using the p1200 silica carbide membrane, with a speckle size $5.6 \mu\text{m} \times 2.9 \mu\text{m}$. Although not illustrated here, a p1500 silica carbide membrane gives also good results. The two cellulose membranes that were tested result in a slightly smaller speckle size, making them better suited for a configuration using a $10\times$ microscope objective. For the cellulose acetate membrane with $1.2 \mu\text{m}$ pore size we would have expected an even smaller speckle size, however at a 555 mm distance from the detector we cannot detect the higher frequencies. In all cases the speckle features appear to be elongated in the horizontal direction as a consequence of the ESRF vertical transverse coherence presently several times better than the horizontal one.

3.3.1. Diamond membrane

Due to the fact that the instrument was conceived to work for different types of X-ray sources, including those with a very high flux, efforts were made to design a membrane that would not be thermally affected by the X-ray exposure. The solution found was a *diamond membrane*, which basically consists of enclosing a certain quantity of diamond powder within two very thin diamond windows. The prototype we designed used 56 g of diamond powder with particle size between 10-20 μm sandwiched between two CVD diamond windows, 9 mm in diameter and 100 μm thick, resulting in an overall membrane thickness of $\sim 740 \mu\text{m}$ placed in a hollowed metal holder.

Figure 3.8: Diamond membrane with metallic holder (front and side views)

This diamond membrane was initially commissioned at the ESRF rendering a speckle size of 5.0 μm horizontally and 7.7 μm vertically and later used during experimental campaigns at the European XFEL and at LCLS. Fig. 3.9 shows speckle images obtained with the membrane at three different sources.

Figure 3.9: Images of speckle patterns generated with the diamond membrane

3.4. Detector Distortion

The first tests focused on the detector calibration and on computing its distortion. The following examples are calculated from data collected at the ESRF during different experiments performed between November 2016 and December 2017. Figures 3.10 and 3.11 show successful computations of the integrated distortion maps for the first and second detectors. Tests conducted using other datasets from experiments where different detector configurations were used rendered equally good results. The resulting distortion maps are used as input for the wavefront recovery software to undistort the images before further computations.

Figure 3.10: Integrated distortion maps of the first detector in a configuration based on a PCO 2000 camera, a $5\times$ microscope objective and a $50\ \mu\text{m}$ thick YAG:Ce scintillator (all axes in pixels)

Figure 3.11: Integrated distortion maps of the second detector in a configuration based on a PCO EDGE 4.2 camera, a $10\times$ microscope objective and a $10\ \mu\text{m}$ LSO:Tb scintillator (all axes in pixels)

4. Experiments and Results

As previously mentioned, the instrument was tested at three X-ray sources: the BM05 beamline of the ESRF, the FXE instrument of the European XFEL and XPP instrument of the LCLS. The results obtained during each of these experimental campaigns are detailed below.

The initial project also included testing the instrument at a laser-powered X-ray source such as the ones housed by ELI-Beamlines in the Czech Rep. It was attempted to reach an agreement with ELI-Beamlines in this respect and negotiations were held in the second half of 2017. Finally, due to their heavy commissioning schedule no adequate slot could be found for our experiment. In search for an alternative source, we contacted at the beginning of 2018 three other facilities: LOA in France, CALA in Germany and the laser-betatron beamline at ALLS/INRS in Canada. The first two facilities refused our request due to technical reasons, but a campaign was scheduled at the Canadian beamline for April 2018. Unfortunately, this experiment was cancelled in March 2018 due the host facility experiencing unexpected and severe technical difficulties forcing them to cancel all experiments until October 2018. The final outcome was that this experiment could not be carried out within the deadlines of the EUCALL project despite our best efforts.

4.1. Commissioning at the ESRF Beamline BM05

As part of the EUCALL grant agreement, the ESRF granted 14 days of beamtime at its beamline BM05 in order to commission the instrument. These dedicated experiments took place between November 2016 and April 2018. The ESRF bending magnet beamline BM05 offers a broad energy spectrum ranging from 6 keV to 60 keV (the full beamline parameters are presented in Table 4.1). There, we tested the various components constituting our instrument (such as scintillators and mirrors), performed the detector calibration and implemented a double triggering scheme required for a dual camera setup.

Source	Bending Magnet
Magnetic field	0.82 T
Radius of curvature	24.593 m
Critical energy	19.87 keV
Maximum flux	2.7×10^{13} ph./s/mrad ² /0.1%BW (white beam)
Monochromaticity ($[\Delta E/E]$)	2.1×10^{-4} (Double crystal Si(111) monochromator) 3.7×10^{-2} (Double-multilayer monochromator)
Energy range (keV)	6–60 keV (Double crystal Si(111) monochromator) 6–30 keV (Double-multilayer monochromator)
Distance from source	27.22 m (Double crystal Si(111) monochromator) 28.4 m (Double-multilayer monochromator)
Unfocused beam size (H×V)	270 μm × 80 μm
Divergence (H×V)	2.4 mrad × 180 μrad

Table 4.1.: X-ray parameters of the ESRF beamline BM05

Figure 4.1: Reconstruction showing the influence of a 500 μm 2D CR on the beam wavefront measured in absolute metrology mode at the beamline BM05 of the ESRF

This commissioning period permitted the acquisition of a large number of datasets which were necessary for testing and debugging of the wavefront reconstruction software. Figure 4.1 presents an example of a reconstructed wavefront from a beam with an 500 μm 2D CRL inserted into it. The data was acquired in the absolute metrology mode using two PCO EDGE 4.2 cameras. One can notice that in this case the lens' contribution to the wavefront dominates the rest of the distortions over the usable region of interest (ROI). The ROI in this case was smaller than the lens aperture, i.e. of 1.5 mm \times 1.5 mm, due to the use of a pierced mirror with a 1.5 mm diameter hole in first detector optics which limited the field of view. However, the use of a pierced mirror was necessary to ensure a higher flux on the second detector in the case of lower photon energies (see Sec. 3.2.3 for details). A wider ROI would allow to observe the contribution of other beamline components to the global wavefront. This effect is more noticeable in Fig. 4.7 as discussed later in this chapter.

Figure 4.2 was produced from data obtained in the differential mode with a 50 μm 2D CRL [15] inserted in and later removed from the collimated X-ray beam. Here, the lens represents the only contribution to the wavefront difference whereas the ROI is wider than the area occupied by the lens.

Figure 4.2: Reconstruction showing the influence of a 2D CRL on the on the beam wavefront measured within the differential metrology mode at the BM05 beamline of the ESRF [15]

4.2. Experiments at the FXE instrument of the European XFEL

The European XFEL (European XFEL) is an X-ray Free Electron Laser located in Schenefeld, Germany, that started user operation in September 2017. This large-scale facility is a source capable of generating ultrashort and extremely bright hard X-ray pulses that can be used for many novel scientific studies, such as the structural analysis of non-crystallized biomolecules, the study of ultra-fast chemical dynamics and the investigation of extreme states of matter by creating transient physical conditions.

The Femtosecond X-Ray Experiments (FXE) instrument at the European XFEL was designed to enable ultrafast pump–probe experiments on ultrafast timescales, dedicated mainly to dynamic studies of chemical and biochemical reactions in liquids and some solid-state applications. The instrument features two independent secondary X-ray emission spectrometers and a 1-Mpx detector for scattering studies. Using a powerful laser as pump source, it can achieve femtosecond time resolution, for X-ray diffraction, X-ray diffuse scattering, wide-angle X-ray scattering, X-ray emission and absorption spectroscopy [24]. The main specifications and beam parameters currently available at FXE are summarized in the Table 4.2 below.

Bandwidth $\Delta E/E$	1×10^{-3} , with natural FEL source
Photon energy range	~ 9.3 keV
Repetition rate	1.1 MHz
Pulses per train	30
Pulse energy (intensity)	300-1000 μ J
Polarization	Linear (horizontal)
X-ray pulse duration	1–300 fs FWHM
Beam size	1–300 μ m adjustable (via several Be lenses)

Table 4.2.: FXE instrument specifications in January 2018

From an optical point of view, the FXE instrument is located at a distance 900 m from the SASE1 source. From the source to the experimental hutch, the beam is deflected twice by a set of offset mirrors, one located at 270 m from the source and the other 10 m further downstream, to eliminate the bremsstrahlung. A third mirror located at 370 m from the source is used to steer the beam to the FXE hutch. Two sets of lens stacks, one located close to the undulator source, i.e. at 230 m from it and another in the beamline hutch, are employed to focus the X-ray beam onto the sample [25]. All these optical components can introduce optical aberrations. The latter could be compensated provided the existence of an online metrology method to measure them.

We were granted access to the FXE instrument for testing the wavefront sensor for a total of 8 half-days split into two experiments that took place in July and August 2017. At that time the European XFEL was still under final commissioning and the beam parameters delivered by the machine were those stated in Table 4.3.

Photon energy range	~ 8.25 and ~ 9.1 keV
Repetition rate	1.25 MHz
Pulses per train	1–2
Pulse energy (intensity)	300–440 μJ

Table 4.3.: Beam parameters available at FXE during July-August 2017

The value of the pulse intensity mentioned in this table was measured before the beam entered the hutch, thus the value of the pulse intensity on our detector system located at the back of the hutch was lower, at $\sim 3.5\%$ this value as indicated by the intensity measurements performed by our PUGCA colleagues working on the X-ray Gas Monitor (XGM) [26], also tested during this FXE campaign.

Figure 4.3: Experimental setup used for differential speckle-based wavefront metrology during the second experiment X288 at the FXE instrument of the European XFEL

As described in Sec. 3.2.1, for part of the measurements we used a high speed UHS Hyper Vision HPV-X2 camera to capture and distinguish the individual X-ray pulses produced by the European XFEL. This setup is shown in Fig. 4.3, whilst Fig. 4.4 shows raw data from this camera capturing two consecutive pulses.

Figure 4.4: Two consecutive pulses of a collimated beam, captured with the HPV-X2 camera: 200 ns between frames, 110 ns exposure time. The upper four frames, from left to right, correspond to the first pulse, whereas the lower four frames correspond to the second pulse

One primary objective of these experiments was to test whether wavefront variations could be detected between pulses of the same train. Figure 4.5, left-hand side, shows two corrected and cropped images corresponding to two consecutive pulses. Differential metrology was operated on a pair of consecutive pulses obtained in identical conditions with no alterations along the beam path. The calculated wavefront difference between such a pair is shown on the right-hand side of Fig. 4.5. The measured variations fall below the instrument error threshold (0.01 nm), leading to the conclusion that wavefront variations between two consecutive pulses of a same train cannot be detected with the present instrument. Subsequent tests on a large number of consecutive pulses pairs came to confirm this conclusion. One can explain this phenomenon through the short length of the pulse train (2 pulses) and its overall low intensity leading to a negligible thermal effect on the optical properties of the beamline components over such a short time scale. Optical vibrations of the mechanical components in the MHz regime can also be considered to be of a very small amplitude in this case and thus too small to be sensed. Nevertheless, the future operation of the European XFEL at 2700 pulses per train may very likely lead to wavefront variations between the first and the last pulse of a train.

Figure 4.5: Differential wavefront reconstruction calculated from two consecutive pulses of a train. Data recorded with a fast Shimadzu HPV-X camera at the FXE instrument of the European XFEL.

Figure 4.6: Wavefront reconstruction using measurements in differential mode acquired with a fast Shimadzu HPV-X camera at the FXE instrument of the European XFEL

Figure 4.6 shows two input images from the Shimadzu HPV-X camera recorded with and without the presence of lanthanum hexaboride (LaB_6) calibration powder in the beam. Such reconstruction permits to isolate the LaB_6 contribution to the wavefront distortion. For absolute wavefront metrology at FXE/European XFEL, we used the double detector setup (as described in Sec. 3.2.1). Because the working photon energy imposed by the machine was 9.1 keV, the absorption of the air turned out to be significant due to the combined presence along the beam path of the semi-transparent 4mm vitreous carbon mirror and of the scintillator of the first detector. This resulted in a low number of counts on the second detector, making the use of the XST method based on only two input images not feasible. To cope with this low pulse intensity, we used sets of images from each detector and applied the more robust but also demanding XSVT method. Figure 4.7 shows the averaged wavefront calculated over several dozens of pulses with this method. Knowing the averaged wavefront is however still very useful when one wants to optimize a beamline. This metrology is sensitive not only to the contribution of a 2D CRL inserted in the beam (main contribution) but also to the other optical elements in the beam path.

Note: The XSVT method will not be included in the software package that will be released at the end of September 2018, as it was not initially planned. However, it could be added in a future release.

Figure 4.7: Reconstruction of a 2D CRL inserted in the beam from absolute wavefront measurements at the FXE instrument of the European XFEL using the XSVT method

4.3. Experiment at the XPP instrument of the LCLS

The Linac Coherent Light Source (LCLS) is a X-ray Free Electron Laser facility that became operational in 2009, as part of the SLAC National Accelerator Laboratory located in Menlo Park, California. This source can generate 120 pulses per second with a peak brilliance of 2×10^{33} photons / s / mm² / mrad² / 0.1% bandwidth.

The present speckle-based wavefront sensor was tested at the X-ray Pump-Probe (XPP) instrument of the LCLS as part of the three half-day experiment that took place between May and June 2018. This beamtime was granted for proposal number X288 which was a joint effort (see Ch. 6) aiming at the characterization of pulsed wavefronts through different methods. The X-ray parameters and capabilities of the XPP instrument [27] are summarized in Table 4.4. Figure 4.8 is a photograph of the experimental setup used during the experiment, featuring two detectors based on Andor Zyla 5.5 cameras. The first detector was semi-transparent, using a 25 μ m YAG:Ce scintillator and a pierced silica substrate mirror with a 1.5 mm hole.

Mirrors, incidence angle	$2 \times$ SiC on Si, 1.32 mrad
Monochromaticity ($[\Delta E/E]$)	1×10^{-3} (SASE), 2×10^{-4} (seeding)
Energy range (keV)	4 to 11 (fundamental)
Unfocused beam size (μ m)	500 at 8.3 keV
Focused beam size (μ m)	2–500
Focusing capability	Be lenses, 1D and 2D focusing
Flux (photons pulse ⁻¹)	1×10^{12} (fundamental)
Pulse length (fs)	5–200
Repetition rate	120, 60, 30, 10, 5, 1, on demand
Optical laser pulse energy (mJ)	20 (800 nm), 4–5 (400 nm), 1 (266 nm)
Optical laser pulse width (fs)	10–150

Table 4.4.: X-ray parameters and capabilities of the XPP instrument [27]

Photon energy	\sim 9.5 keV
Repetition rate	120 Hz (effective 30 Hz, chopper)
Pulse energy (intensity) [28]	200 μ J

Table 4.5.: Beam parameters available at XPP during 28-31 May 2018

Figure 4.8: Experimental setup used for absolute speckle-based wavefront metrology during experiment X288 at the XPP instrument of the LCLS

This experiment followed similar objectives as the one at the European XFEL. Figure 4.9 shows a wavefront reconstruction obtained in the differential mode corresponding to the contribution of a phase plate introduced into the beam to compensate for a rotationally symmetric aberration produced by the lens stack. Figure 4.10 shows the wavefront reconstruction in absolute mode corresponding to the beam produced by the LCLS, featuring the combined contribution of all beamline elements including the stack of 20 CRL lenses with $R = 50 \mu\text{m}$. When comparing to Fig. 4.1 and 4.7, one can observe that such a focused beam produces a strongly curved wavefront. Moreover, although the working energy was similar to the one used in Sec. 4.2, the flux at XPP combined with the use of a thin scintillator and a pierced mirror, made possible the single pulse metrology using XST in absolute mode. Conversely, this was hard to achieve during the experiment at the European XFEL since the semi-transparent optics was not fully optimized for the 8-10 keV energy range at that time and because the European XFEL was not yet operating at its full capacity with a pulse energy lower than expected. The positive results obtained from the LCLS data validate that the detector in its present design is suitable for single pulse XST metrology at XFEL-type hard X-ray sources under normal operating conditions.

Figure 4.9: Two and three dimensional rendering of a wavefront reconstruction, showing the contribution of a phase plate introduced in the beam to correct for a rotationally symmetric aberration, measured using the differential metrology mode at the XPP instrument of the LCLS

Figure 4.10: Wavefront reconstruction showing the highly collimated beam produced by a stack of $20 \times 50 \mu\text{m}$ CRL lenses, measured using the absolute metrology mode at the beamline XPP of the LCLS

5. Conclusions and Outlook

The speckle-based wavefront sensor described in this document focuses on using the XST method for single pulse wavefront metrology in the hard X-ray energy range. The instrument has been successfully tested at a synchrotron facility and two different X-ray free electron lasers sources. Solutions were proposed to overcome or alleviate technical challenges that may arise when implementing this device. That includes dealing with the high absorption of the first detector in the 8-10 keV X-ray energy range, choosing a suitable speckle membrane, finding appropriate cameras for high and very high repetition rates and implementing a double triggering scheme. A limiting factor of the instrument for single pulse metrology is the requirement of a photon flux of at least 10^9 photons / s / mm² / mrad² over a $\sim 10\%$ bandwidth at the level of the first detector. This becomes more difficult to achieve in the lower energy range of the instrument and when other optical components present along the beam path absorb photons. In the scenario of a low photon flux available, the minimum flux condition could be relaxed by using the XSVT method that provides an average wavefront over several pulses. This can be a viable solution when pulse to pulse metrology is not an imperative.

The instrument could not be tested at a laser-based X-ray source due to incompatibilities with the ELI-Beamlines (Czech Rep.) commissioning schedule and due to severe technical issues suffered by the alternative host facility, the laser-betatron beamline at the ALLS/INRS (Canada). Yet, we consider such an experiment as feasible although the high divergence of some of these sources would require making appropriate changes to the setup, e.g. tuning the pixel size of the second detector to compensate for the high divergence.

Regarding the software package, we obtained good results during tests using data acquired from our experiments, as can be seen in the many examples of detector calibration maps and reconstructed wavefronts presented in this report. After the code release in September 2018, we foresee more functionalities that could be added to expand its use beyond the XST method. In terms of processing speed, as shown in Chap. 2.4 and 2.5, through the work of our colleagues from WP5 UFDAC, much could be gained in terms of optimizing the software package provided that additional resources in terms of time and manpower will be granted. Workflow-wise the Python interface is preferable as it helps making the code more readable especially in view of an open-source release. However, for intensive and recurrent use under experimental conditions,

especially at high and very high repetition sources, a full GPU-based solution written in C/C++ would be a much better suited solution. The current work done by J. Schenke helped improve the overall performance of the original code and solved some bottlenecks. Even so, better processing times could be obtained by employing a full high performance solution.

5.1. Synergy aspects

The proposed wavefront sensor prototype is valid over a broad range of energies, from 8 keV to 25 keV, and can be adapted to fit the needs of different X-ray research infrastructures (RIs). The results presented in this report include solutions for implementing the wavefront sensor at synchrotrons and X-ray free-electron laser facilities. The successful completion of these experiments has been a direct consequence of the collaboration between different teams and different institutions within the EUCALL project. Knowledge exchange concerning the requirements and transferability of wavefront sensing techniques between the different RIs (ESRF, European XFEL, DESY, Elletra, ELI) was ensured through joint discussions on this topic during the EUCALL midterm and annual meetings and during other satellite meetings (e.g. at PhotonDiag 2017). More specifically for the speckle-based wavefront sensor, this topic was discussed in depth with colleagues from the European XFEL and ELI, during meetings, teleconferences and via email, in view of setting up wavefront sensing experiments at their facilities. Although the planned experiment at a laser-powered X-ray source could not be executed, the implementation of the instrument at such a facility has been studied and is considered to be feasible. Thus, the entire community of different types of RIs that form EUCALL can benefit from this research.

6. Acknowledgements

The work presented in this report is the result of joined efforts from many people and of a collaboration between several institutions. The authors of this section would like to acknowledge all those who have been involved in any of the design, assembly, test or optimization stage of the instrument.

From the ESRF, we thank: Thierry Martin, Margie Olbinado, Roberto Homs, Manuel Perez, Luca Capasso, José-Maria Clement, Christophe Jarnias, Paul-Antoine Douissard, Eric Mathieu, Michael Krisch, Alexander Rack, Thomas Roth, Rafael Celestre, Yves Watier, Samuel da Cunha, Pierre Piau, Fernando Calvelo Vazquez, Patrick Meritto, Antoine Meritto.

We also acknowledge and thank our colleagues from HZDR, Jonas Schenke and Michael Bussmann, members of EUCALL WP5: UFDAC, for their study on the optimization possibilities of the code and their significant contributions to Sec. 2.4 and 2.5 of this report.

For access and support during the commissioning experiments at the FXE instrument of the XFEL, we are grateful to Christian Bressler, Sebastian Schulz, Andreas Galler, Frederico Alves Lima, Dmitry Khakhulin, Wojciech Gawelda.

We acknowledge our colleagues during the X288 experiment at the LCLS beamline XPP: Matthew Seaberg, Patrik Vagovic, Andrew Aquila, Juraj Krempasky, Andreas Jaggi, Frank Seiboth, Uwe Flechsig, Zhu Diling, Changyong Song, Anne Sakdinawat, Bob Nagler, Hae Ja Lee, Sebastien Boutet, Daniele Coco, Christian David, Jacek Krzywinski, Ulrich Wagner, Philip Heimann.

Although we did not manage to test our instrument at a laser-based X-ray source, we would like to thank our colleagues from the ELI-Beamlines for the efforts they deployed for our attempt: Jakob Andreasson, Uddhab Chaulagain, Martin Přeček, Jaroslav Nejdml, and the scientists from the laser-betatron beamline of the ALLS/INRS in Canada: Jean Claude Kieffer and Sylvain Fourmaux, for their help in attempting to organize those experimental campaigns.

Finally, we wish to thank the EUCALL-PUCCA management team for their support throughout the project: Stephan Klumpp, Graham Appleby and Kai Tiedtke.

References

- [1] H. Winnick, *Particle Accelerator Conference*, IEEE (1997).
- [2] P. Mercere, et al., *Proc.SPIE* **5921**, 10 (2005) 10.1117/12.622799.
- [3] B. Flöter, et al., *New Journal of Physics* **12**, 083015 (2010).
- [4] M. Idir, et al., *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research A* **616**, 162–171 (2010) 10.1016/j.nima.2009.10.168.
- [5] S. Rutishauser, et al., *Nature Communications* **3**, 947, 947 (2012) 10.1038/ncomms1950.
- [6] S. Berujon, et al., *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation* **22**, 886–894 (2015) 10.1107/S1600577515005433.
- [7] S. Bérujon, et al., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **108**, 158102 (2012) 10.1103/PhysRevLett.108.158102.
- [8] *OpenCV-Python: Template Matching*, http://opencv-python-tutroals.readthedocs.io/en/latest/py_tutorials/py_imgproc/py_template_matching/py_template_matching.html, Accessed: March 13th, 2018.
- [9] *OpenCV: Template Matching*, https://docs.opencv.org/2.4/doc/tutorials/imgproc/histograms/template_matching/template_matching.html, Accessed: March 13th, 2018.
- [10] R. T. Frankot, et al., *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.* **10**, 439–451 (1988) 10.1109/34.3909.
- [11] P. O’Leary, et al., in *IEEE Indian Conference on Computer Vision, Graphics and Image Processing* (2008).
- [12] P. O’Leary, et al., *IEEE T. Instrumentation and Measurement* **61**, 1237–1251 (2012).
- [13] C. Jordan, *pyGrad2Surf*, <https://github.com/cjordan/pyGrad2Surf>, Accessed: March 13th, 2018.
- [14] J. Schenke, “Parallelisierung des Wellenfrontrekonstruktionsalgorithmus auf Multicore-Prozessoren”, bachelor thesis (Technische Universität Dresden, Mar. 2018).
- [15] T. Roth, et al., *X-ray Refractive Lenses Metrology. Experiment at BM05, ESRF* (Apr. 2017).
- [16] O. Grisel, et al., *Embarrassingly parallel for loops*, <https://github.com/joblib/joblib/blob/master/doc/parallel.rst#old-multiprocessing-backend>, Accessed: February 24th, 2018.
- [17] J. Schenke, *CPU Utilization*, https://github.com/ComputationalRadiationPhysics/Wavefront-Sensor/blob/f2fc5c2e5f8b4ef0e9b3ca3a4e770db67f230588/doc/cpu_util.md, (Private), 2018.
- [18] S. Berujon, et al., *Phys. Rev. Applied* **5**, 044014 (2016) 10.1103/PhysRevApplied.5.044014.
- [19] U. Bonse, et al., *Progress in biophysics and molecular biology* **65** 1-2, 133–69 (1996).

- [20] C. Robertson, et al., *Journal of Biomedical Optics* **17**, (2012) 10.1117/1.JBO.17.8.080801.
- [21] A. Hamed, *Opt. Photonics J.* **3**, 250–258 (2013) 10.4236/opj.2013.33040.
- [22] M.-C. Zdora, et al., *Journal of Applied Physics* **118**, 113105 (2015) 10.1063/1.4931145.
- [23] T. L. Alexander, et al., *Appl. Opt.* **33**, 8240–8250 (1994) 10.1364/AO.33.008240.
- [24] https://www.xfel.eu/facility/instruments/fxe/index_eng.html, Accessed: June 2018.
- [25] https://www.xfel.eu/facility/instruments/fxe/instrument_design/index_eng.html, Accessed: June 2018.
- [26] S. Klumpp, et al., *Deliverable D7.4. XGM prototype: calibrated and tested*, https://www.eucall.eu/sites/sites_custom/site_eucall/content/e21597/e25317/e66312/EUCALL_WP7_PUCCA_Deliverable_7_4_D23_28_03_2018.pdf?preview=preview, Mar. 2018.
- [27] M. Chollet, et al., *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation* **22**, 503–507 (2015) 10.1107/S1600577515005135.
- [28] https://portal.slac.stanford.edu/sites/lclscore_public/Accelerator_Physics_Published_Documents/LCLS-parameters-3-22-17.pdf, Accessed: June 2018.

Part II.

Activity report on Wavefront sensing at FERMI

Authors: Michele Manfredda, Lorenzo Raimondi and Marco Zangrando

The activities of FERMI were aimed at the realization of an analysis software for wavefront sensing (WFS) that will be compatible with third-party Hartmann sensors, and to its validation by means of independent techniques. The motivation of the activity lays in the growing interest in applying WFS to the characterization of HHG and FEL sources, thus outdoing the usual scope of Hartmann WFS (used for optical systems optimization). For such a purpose, versatile and well known algorithms are preferable over closed commercial software.

At FERMI we have implemented a hybrid Python-MATLAB package that accomplish the key steps of data acquisition and analysis, namely:

1. centroid recognition.
2. slope detection.
3. wavefront reconstruction.
4. wavefront backpropagation.
5. decomposition into Zernike polynomials (exploiting python community libraries).

Figure 1: Workflow diagram of the FERMI WFS software

Test measurements were performed with a Hartmann sensor (Imagine Optic, 72x72 grid, pitch = 180 μm , operating in the wavelength range 4-40 nm). The sensor is plugged downstream the bendable KB of the DiProI beamline onto a angular-translational stage, which allows to perfectly match the incoming radiation direction. The radiation is collected approximately 1.2 m after the focal point (i.e. diverging again). The corresponding electromagnetic field (amplitude and phase) is numerically backpropagated via Fresnel Transform to a set of planes in the proximity of the expected focal plane. The latter is computed from the wavefront curvature radius. The reconstructed spots were compared with PMMA ablation imprints and with diffraction images produced with via a novel kind of variable line-spacing (VLS) gratings [1].

Figure 2: Comparison of the intensity distribution in the focal plane between (a) Hartmann sensor with in-house software and (b) PMMA ablation imprints (measured via AFM). The ablation imprint is obtained by minimizing the imprint size while moving the PMMA-sample along the optical axis (c). The images are singularly normalized to unity. Scalar bars correspond to 10 μm .

Figure 2 shows the intensity distribution at the focal plane obtained (a) via numerical reconstructions (using our in-house package) and (b) by means of single-shot ablation imprint. The wavelength used is 30.2 nm. The reconstruction from WFS data is in agreement with the PMMA imprint, yielding a similar beam estimation of the beam size (Estimated FWHM of the central spot : 5.7x6.5 μm^2 from WFS reconstruction, 5.5x6.3 μm^2 from ablation imprint). In addition, finer structures due to interference effects are also correctly reproduced. The origin of such structures is ascribed to a combined effect of the KB figure error and diffraction from the KB geometrical aperture (smaller than the beam size).

Further tests were performed by combining Hartmann WFS with a VLS grating, which is engineered to generate a focused off-axis image of the beam. Such an approach, allowing real-time analysis, represents an interesting alternative to ex-situ technique, such as ablation, although it may suffer of beam instabilities and alignment issues. Measurements are performed at the wavelength of 20.8 nm, with another set of KB mirrors. Figure 3 shows a comparison of the two approaches in assessing the intensity distribution at different positions along the longitudinal (z) axis. The field detected with the WFS is numerically back-propagated for different values of z, whereas the diffracted intensity distribution is probed by moving the grating. The agreement between the two dataset validates the effectiveness of the reconstruction algorithm even for off-focus reconstruction. Possible future activities at FERMI may involve the test of the algorithm for real-time machine tuning and possibly independent calibration tests of Hartmann detectors by mean of HHG sources.

Figure 3: Comparison between (a) multi-shot diffracted intensity distribution from the VLS grating and (b) single-shot intensity distribution reconstructed from Hartmann data, with in-house software. Scalar bars correspond to 10 μm . Grating images appear to be blurred due to angular jitter of the source [1].

References

- [1] M. Schneider, et al., [Nature Communications](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-02567-0) **9**, 2041–1723 (2018) [10.1038/s41467-017-02567-0](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-02567-0).

Part III.

Report on Focal spot characterization using wavefront sensors at FLASH2 and WavePropagator Code

Authors: M. Ruiz-Lopez, B. Keitel, M. Kuhlmann, S. Dziarzhytski, E. Plönjes, T.

Wodzinski, J. Chalupský, T. Burian, V. Vozda, L. Vyšín, V. Hájková, L. Juha, M.

Zangrando, L. Raimondi, L. Samoylova

At the open port beamline FL24 at FLASH2, a Kirk-Patrick Baez (KB) focusing system was installed in collaboration with the team of Fermi@Elettra (M. Zangrando et al.). For the characterization of the focus, the FLASH group used three different methods: i) the back-propagation tool of the wavefront sensor software, ii) measuring series of PMMA imprints for different wavelength and different settings and iii) comparing both methods with the wavefront simulations code WavePropagator.

DESY developed a compact Hartmann wavefront sensor (WFS) for the soft x-ray spectral range ($\lambda=6-40$ nm) in collaboration with the Laser-Laborium Göttingen e.V. [1]. The Hartmann plate in the WFS divides the incoming radiation from the Free electron laser (FEL) into sub rays and illuminates a phosphor coated CCD chip. From lateral deviations in the beam spot pattern, the wavefront for single pulses is reconstructed using a modal approach. Second moment beam parameters such as beam width, divergence, Rayleigh length, waist position, waist size and M^2 are calculated, as well as aberrations of the optical system. Back-propagation in the near field is calculated using Fresnel propagation with fast Fourier and beam transformation.

The PMMA imprint was carried out by the group of J. Chalupský from the Institute of Physics, AS CR Prague [2].

The simulation code WavePropagator (WPG) was developed in the European XFEL for beamline scientists at Free Electron Lasers [3]. It is based on the Synchrotron Radiation Workshop (SRW) code and run on Python structures. The wavefront propagation is described with the Huygens-Fresnel principle along x and y direction. The Fourier optics approach is used for describing the interaction of the radiation in each individual optical element. The code provides information about the intensity and the phase and includes the definition of several optics e.g. elliptical, planar, and spherical mirrors, gratings etc. The FLASH group implemented an update in WPG, allowing simulations containing misalignments in the optics, i.e., yaw, roll and pitch. Fig. 1 shows an array of images obtained in FLASH1. The stripes correspond to diffraction effects due to the mirror's figure of error. A perfect alignment would show the same stripes but perfectly aligned at 90° . However, the simulations show that the mirror is rotated along the horizontal axis 4 mrad in roll and 2 mrad in pitch. The new upgraded version of WPG provides calculations of the beam with high precision, making the code a robust tool for predicting the behavior of beam propagation. In this sense, WPG is an ideal tool to complement the characterization of the focus at FL24.

Figure 1: Beam shapes along the caustic of an elliptical mirror at BL3 at FLASH1. a) Experimental data and b) Simulations

Fig. 2 shows the layout of the beam path from the source to the focus position of the KB optic system at the end of the beamline FL24. The wavefront sensor was mounted 2 m downstream of the focus while the PMMA imprint setup was placed in the focus position. All measurements were performed for the 2m-focus point settings of the KB optic system.

Figure 2: Layout of the beamline FL24 at FLASH2

Figure 3: Comparison of the three methods used for characterizing the focus of the Kirkpatrick-Baez optics installed in FLASH2. a) Simulations with WavePropagator code, b) Back-propagation measurements using the wavefront sensor and c) PMMA imprints.

The wavefront reconstruction, as well as the beam parameters were calculated from second order moments using Born-Wolf reconstruction with expansion 6. The divergence as the full opening angle and all beam diameters are given by the WFS software in 4σ , i.e., $\theta_{div@x}=4.25$ mrad, $\theta_{div@y}=3.25$ mrad. The three caustic profiles agree well both in shape and size, even when different apertures are used.

The back-propagation measurements of single shot Hartmann wavefront measurements were done at wavelength $\lambda=13.5$ nm and with aperture $\Theta=8.8$ mm placed in front of the KB optic system. The focus is presented in the middle position in Fig. 3. At this position the back-propagation of the WFS shows that the waist in x is approximately $w_x\sim 5.9$ μm (fwhm) and the waist in y is $w_y\sim 8.8$ μm (fwhm). The beam profile at three different positions (18 mm

upstream, at focus and 21 mm downstream) along the caustic is shown. These measurements and the simulations are compared to the caustic measurements given by the PMMA imprints (right row in Fig. 3) in order to assess techniques for evaluation of the focus size and the focus position.

The WPG code and the back propagation analysis of the wavefront sensor concur also for different apertures as shown in Fig. 4. For bigger apertures the diffraction is observable only along x and y direction. For higher apertures the diffraction effects are noticeable around all the main center spot. This is due to the fact that for bigger apertures there is only scattering in the beam caused by the figure of error of the mirrors. However, smaller apertures produce diffraction effects that enclose the maximum intensity spot. We observe that simulations and measurements with the wavefront sensor match also well in dimensions. Those simulations were carried out for wavelength $\lambda=13.5$ nm and source divergence $\theta_{div}=120$ μ rad.

Figure 4: Back-propagation measurements using the Wavefront sensor (up) and simulations using WavePropaGator for different apertures

We conclude that the upgrade in the WPG code is satisfactory and the code is trustable enough to be used for the reconstruction of the full propagation of the beam and to predict the behavior of the FEL when the users request new setups. Further analysis and paper preparation is ongoing.

Acknowledgements. This project was also partially supported by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 730872.

References

- [1] B. Keitel, et al., *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation* **23**, 43–49 (2016) [10.1107/S1600577515020354](#).
- [2] J. Chalupský, et al., *Opt. Express* **15**, 6036–6043 (2007) [10.1364/OE.15.006036](#).
- [3] L. Samoylova, et al., *Journal of Applied Crystallography* **49**, 1347–1355 (2016) [10.1107/S160057671600995X](#).

